

Table S1. Summary of CRM elemental associations, host lithologies, and representative localities in the NE Estonian basement domains and the Märjamaa–Kloostri rapakivi system

Geological domain / intrusion	Element association / key metals	Reported concentrations / enrichment	Host lithology (as described in text)	Representative localities
Alutaguse Domain (metavolcanics)	Cu–Zn–Pb	Cu 2230 ppm; Zn 2650 ppm; Pb 4030 ppm	Magnetite-rich gneisses; sulphide-graphite gneisses	Haljala; Assamalla; Uljaste
Alutaguse Domain (metasediments)	Ni–Cu–Zn–Pb	Ni 385 ppm; Cu 1060 ppm; Zn 4100 ppm; Pb 1430 ppm	Low-SiO ₂ Fe–Mg–S-rich metasedimentary units	Haljala; Uljaste
Tallinn–Alutaguse domains (MSCL-XYZ)	Ni–Co–Cr	Anomalous relative to felsic/metasedimentary background	Mafic to Mg-rich metavolcanics and intrusions	Haljala
Tallinn–Alutaguse–Jõhvi domains (MSCL-XYZ)	Ti–V–Fe	Concentrated anomalies	Magnetite-rich gneisses and Fe-quartzites	Haljala; Jõhvi
Tallinn structural zone (MSCL-XYZ)	Mo–W–Bi	Localised enrichments	Shear-zone-related gneisses	Haljala; Tallinn structural zone
Alutaguse Domain (MSCL-XYZ)	Sn–Zn–Cd (In)	Clustered anomalies	Sulphide-graphite gneisses	Uljaste; Viru-Nigula
Alutaguse Domain (MSCL-XYZ)	Cu–Ni	Anomalous associations	Mafic–ultramafic intrusive bodies	Haljala; Assamalla
Tallinn–Alutaguse domains (MSCL-XYZ)	Nb–Y–P	REE-bearing associations	Metasedimentary units and granitoid-proximal lithologies	Haljala; Assamalla; Uljaste
Tallinn–Alutaguse domains (MSCL-XYZ)	Au–Ag–As–Sb–Bi–W–Se–Sn	Multi-element hydrothermal associations	Hydrothermally altered gneisses	Haljala; Uljaste
Märjamaa rapakivi pluton (Phase I)	REE–HFSE; Fe–Ti–P	ΣREE up to ~3600 ppm	Si-poor, Fe–Ti–P-rich ferroan granitoids	Märjamaa
Jõhvi Domain	Fe-oxide–S	Strong remanent magnetisation	Magnetite-rich gneisses and quartzites	Jõhvi magnetic anomaly